

ISSUES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Nurimova Ayzada Razatdinovna

Student at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, English Language and Literature

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
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ABSTRACT

Language is the soul of the whole nation. Today, attention to learning and teaching national and foreign languages is one of the most urgent issues. Therefore, in this article, the use of works of art and the lives of writers used in teaching English plays an important role. This article has some thoughts on this.

INTRODUCTION

Today, we are living in such a time that requires pedagogues to equip young people not only with national values, but also with modern knowledge in accordance with the needs of the times. After all, M. Behbudi also emphasized that "secular science and science are necessary to survive in the world, a nation without modern science and science will be destroyed by others."

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, according to general recognition, there is no need to prove that the 21st century is turning into the age of globalization and the era of the disappearance of borders, the age of information and communication technologies and the Internet, and the age of ever-increasing competition in the world arena and the world market.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Along with mother tongue and literature, English language and literature, cultural traditions are taught in schools. The works of English writers are widely used in this field.

English writer Charles Dickens was born on February 7, 1812 in Portsmouth, England, in the Dickens family. In his works, Dickens highlighted the social and spiritual life of the English society in the 21st century. Writer's "The Pickwick Papers", "Oliver Twist", "The life and Adventure of Nicholas Nickleby", "David Copperfield", "Great expectations" and other works are very popular.

"Great Expectations" by Charles Dickens is one of the most popular works among Uzbek readers. It describes the social life of Great Britain in the 19th century. In the work, the writer sharply condemns the differences between the rich and the poor in the English society, the struggles between the classes, what human dreams and aspirations can make him capable of, and the injustices in the society. In this work, the writer described the whole reality and his child's attitude to life in all its aspects. When we read the work, sometimes it brings a sweet

smile to our lips, and sometimes it brings a sarcastic smile. Pip's simple idea that life should continue as it is in his imagination changes as a result of his meeting with other characters of the play. In the end, Pip becomes a person who keeps his thoughts to himself and does not comment on what is happening in society. The writer showed that this work can happen to any person living in the entire English society in the character of Pip. Thousands of works of not only Charles Dickens, but also other representatives of English literature, which have been preserved for centuries, leave an indelible mark on the hearts of readers and invite a person to think deeply. Therefore, it is important for Uzbek students to familiarize themselves with the works of these great writers in order to receive education in accordance with the requirements of the present time.

Through the reading of short stories, plays, and novels, which often try to portray the society in some realistic way, students have a glimpse of the culture of the native speakers of English. The conversations give them the nuances used by the native speakers of English in performing various roles in the society. They learn the social etiquette and the words, sentences, tone, and tenor, which go with the etiquette [2].

With the study of literature, the second/foreign language learners of English are introduced to the historical as well as the current culture of the English speaking peoples. Through the culture, they also come to know and understand the worldview of the native speakers. No language makes sense to its learner without some understanding of the worldview it represents.

English speaking peoples do have a unique history, even though the Europeans may share aspects of this history in general. This is not unlikely that many TESOL students may or may not show any interest at all the English literature. The learners may come to a SL/FL class simply to learn the language to meet practical needs. Many students are able to hold their attention and progress further in acquiring another language only if the materials are exposed to be interesting, not just meet their practical ends.

With the study of literature, the second/ foreign language learners of English are introduced to the historical as well as the current culture of the English- speaking people. Through the culture, the learners also come to study and understand the worldview of the native speakers. No language makes sense to its learner without some understanding of the worldview it represents. Thus universally applicable moral and ethical concerns are easily conveyed, raised and impressed in the minds of the learners through English literature, even as they enjoy reading and listening to the stories [4].

A poem readily lends itself for listening and speech practice. As a rule, poems are musical and sweet to hear. Hence, the poem to be taught should be recorded and then played for the benefit of the learners. The learners may be encouraged to listen to the recording as many times as possible. This will not only give them a feel of the music present in the poem but also provide them the much-needed exposure to the sounds of the target language. This is fact that, speech practice may follow listening practice. We should let the learners recite the poem in chorus, then in groups and at last individually. This will enable them to have practice with the target language sounds in a meaningful way. Also, engaging the

learners in a discussion in the class can ensure speaking practices. After they have learnt the poem and got the overall message, they may be asked evaluative questions.

Initially, the learners may be asked to find justifications for their answers from within the text. And, at the next step, they may be allowed to seek justifications from outside the text. This will encourage natural and spontaneous speaking in the class. It is not that only listening and speaking can be promoted with the help of a poem. Reading and writing can also be promoted.

Active listening to the recitation

This is crucial for students to be able to get a feel for the rhythm and sounds of a poem - more so than for most pieces of prose. This isn't always easy in a second language, and so listening to their teacher read the poem, or to a professional recording, perhaps by the poet or by an actor, is, it is, essential [5].

With any listening activity, students will need some kind of preparation and task so that they can be actively engaged. They might be asked to check predictions that arose from a warm-up discussion, to compare their suggested rhyming couplets with the poet's, or to identify stressed words and syllables.

- You might also want to get your students to listen to recorded or live discussions about poems. This can, for example, take the form of a couple of teachers or a group of students giving their views on a poem, or even an interview with the poet.

Active reading of selected poem

Here, reading means extensive reading of the poem. Reading activities can center on not only the poems themselves, but also around background reading sources like biography or criticism [6].

- Teacher should not get stuck in literary analysis unless your students have specifically asked for a literature lesson, but do draw attention to useful syntax, grammar and vocabulary, and beware of common poetic conventions like inverted word order, ensuring that students are aware that this is a deviation from the norms of everyday English language.
- The teacher should avoid too much analysis, which can kill enjoyment, and we are aiming for the opposite! As a pre-reading activity, Teachers may get the students to predict what they are about to read. With poetry, this can be done with the title as a catalyst, by revealing the lines gradually on an overhead projector, or by looking at the first verse of a longer poem. The teacher should refer students back to what they have read in the text so that they are justifying their predictions.

CONCLUSION

Finding appropriate literature to teach in the second language classroom has always been a major challenge. Selected text should not be too long, not too linguistically and conceptually complex, not too distant from the knowledge of the students, and should generate student's interest. Due to these stringent requirements few teachers use literature use literature in the English classroom. However, adequate attention should be paid to the proper text selection. If the text is beyond the level comprehension of the learning, then the purpose of language teaching will also get defeated; therefore, the text should be simple and interesting in keeping with the level of proficiency of the learners.

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